

Supplementary Information of the paper “An experience in mixing cognitive and affective teaching approaches in a CS1 course”

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1. Introduction

This refers to a complementary information set that presents details about background (Section 2), visual integration of the methods (Section 3), students’ profile (Section 4), Lessons Learned (Section 5), and Threats to Validity (Section 6) that appears summarized at the paper above.

2. Background and Motivation

At our university, the *introduction to programming* course aims at presenting programming fundamentals via problems that cover all topics of the current curricula [Sahami et al. 2013]. This 12-week course is core for different academic units at our university, including Computer Science and Biomedical Engineering. After considering the course audience, students’ anecdotal information (e.g., lack of motivation, uninteresting exercises), dropout rate, and short satisfaction surveys, we realized that our teaching approach was not adequate.

Indeed, it did not consider the differences in programming knowledge, personalities, and interests among the students that belong to each academic unit. Our lectures stressed aspects of theoretical programming constructs (e.g., what a loop is and how it works) rather than offering the link between these constructs and their practical contexts (contextualized learning). During lab practices, students worked alone to solve tasks based on mathematical problems. Furthermore, there was no formative feedback systematization at all.

Inspired by this self-reflection, we examined teaching methods and programming problem ideas that could be more appealing for our course audience. Such examination was guided by our belief in the potential of the affective dimension to leverage the learning process. The next section summarizes our findings.

2.1. Theoretical Foundation

The literature presents a large set of pedagogical approaches and tools to engage students in programming learning. Despite that, numerous factors related to students (e.g., learning style, intrinsic motivation, mathematical competence) and environment (e.g., the pedagogical intervention, programming language) contribute to high dropout rates [Patil and Goje 2009]. This scenario suggests that planning introductory programming courses should consider complementary teaching methods to promote learning. This work assumes that learning is active, diverse, inherently social, and dual (involves affective and cognitive spheres) as the basis of our planning.

Pair programming establishes a protocol where students pair on the same computer and interchange roles (*Driver* or *Navigator*) to collaborate actively on solving programming problems [McDowell et al. 2003]. This active learning approach has produced robust pedagogical results, even for non-computer science students [O'Donnell et al. 2015] or students with a different pace of learning [Ayub et al. 2019]. Besides, its social nature makes it suitable for students that prefer to hold a debate.

Teachers can enrich this collaborative meaning construction by providing formative feedback to students in pairs or individually [Hahn et al. 2009]. Since their role in collaborative learning tends to be closer to a coach, teacher's feedback offers an expert examination of students' work. Moreover, this kind of scaffolding can assist and motivate students forward in their learning [Brookhart 2017].

Students and teachers agree that building programs (learning-by-doing) are an effective way of developing programming knowledge [Vihavainen et al. 2011]. Therefore, programming problems should be diverse to allow different students (e.g., motivated by task or non-computer science students) to delve into a more hands-on learning experience [O'Donnell et al. 2015, Baker et al. 2013]. In this sense, formulating programming problems should creatively consider insights from knowledge area problems (e.g., Biology, Engineering) or contextualized mathematical-based problems to be more meaningful and relevant to students.

Finally, learning and teaching activities are not entirely intellectual [Trigwell 2012]. Both require an intense interplay of the cognitive and affective dimensions. Previous studies have demonstrated the relevance of affectivity to the student-subject relationship [Baker et al. 2013]. They also have emphasized the teaching practice as a mediator of this relationship [Amado et al. 2009, da Silva Leite 2014, Shephard 2008]. Furthermore, teaching is an emotionally demanding work because of all intrapersonal and interpersonal emotional experiences lived within the classroom and the academic community [Trigwell 2012, Hargreaves 1998].

3. Visual Integration of *MixOf4* methods

Figure 1 illustrates the integration and simbiotic relationship between the four methods that comprises *MixOf4*.

4. The Students' Profile

To gather student perceptions and feelings about the intervention based on *MixOf4*, we used two non-mandatory Google Forms-based surveys. We opted for this resource to

Figure 1. Visual integration of *MixOf4* methods (Source: The author)

enable students to choose a convenient time to ponder their learning experience.

The pre-course survey comprised two closed-ended questions related to gender and academic unit, plus two Likert scale questions focusing on programming experience and confidence level. Further, the first survey also informed students about the research nature (without revealing details) and requested authorization to use their de-identified and aggregated data.

The post-course survey asked students to express their perceptions about their programming confidence level (Likert question). An open-ended question captured students' criticism, suggestions, or reflections on their own learning experience. Despite the small number of Likert-based questionings, the surveys' internal consistency of 0.71 (Cronbach's Test) is considered a good one [Panayides 2013].

5. Lessons Learned

In this section, we reflect on challenges experienced during the pedagogical intervention based on *MixOf4*. All of them left open questions that we intend to answer as future works.

Providing and receiving textual feedback demonstrated to be detached. We planned and prepared feedback before offering emphatic yet constructive guidance to students. Moreover, we took for granted the empirical evidence that all students would handle feedback actively. However, the frequent contact with the students and survey results revealed that part of students did not use feedback information in their learning process. This situation made us recognize that the use of such information as a learning opportunity about the self requires students' preparation.

Providing feedback and attention equally to each pair in each lab practice was tiring. Conversely, these interactions contributed to strengthening the teacher-student relation and the supportive learning environment. Sharing lab practices with another teacher can be beneficial to reduce the workload and promote diversity in interactions with students [Anderson and Gegg-Harrison 2012]. However, we are curious about which kind of affective implications for students two tutors with different personalities would produce. Moreover, mindfulness practice could be helpful here once we observed that the teacher's

distractive thoughts (about future and past work situations) partially contributed to his tiredness [Jennings 2015].

We had to deal with very few students that *explicitly requested to work alone* in some groups. To address the impacts of this situation, we talked privately to each student to explore any particular reason (e.g., equity [Lewis and Shah 2015], fear to expose a weakness) and reinforced how vital teamwork is. Furthermore, we discreetly followed and acted over these cases during some classes. Despite that, some of these students kept uncooperative behavior. Such cases reminded us that develop collaborative skills (e.g., mutual trust, comfort with interpersonal risks) is challenging and requires more than experiencing pair programming or just hearing about teamwork.

Finally, we had to handle *different students' interaction styles*. Most students gradually developed real affective reciprocity with the teacher while participating in lecture or lab classes. Indeed, some of them still look for us to discuss any subject matter. However, a few students showed no interest (or established limits) in a substantial relationship or dialogue with the teacher. Hence, we employed a style (affectionate or reserved) according to students' inclination. Such situation made us wondered if there are students' factors (e.g., anxiety towards the subject, shyness, particular preference, teacher's personality) that could have caused this detachment and which strategies we could use to reinforce closeness.

6. Threats to Validity

Our study has some threats regarding the number of students (82 students) and the professor-experimenter bias. As the classes and labs related to the three groups lasted for one year and a half, the professor-experimenter may talk and interact differently with each group, which is very natural. Lastly, it is worth noting that students were unaware of the experiment (blinding principle), and we used a preliminary group (a fourth group) to calibrate our approach.

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